

Johannesburg's Air: What People Think and Want

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Executive Summary

Johannesburg's Air: What People Think and Want

Air pollution in Johannesburg is a pressing public health and environmental issue, but it is unclear how much people perceive air pollution, who they believe should take responsibility, and the kinds of air quality policies they are willing to support. We conducted a comprehensive survey (online and in-person) in early 2025 with over 3,000 respondents from the City of Johannesburg to identify their perceptions of localised air quality and their policy preferences.

High level of concern about air pollution: A strong majority of Johannesburg respondents are deeply concerned about air pollution. Approximately **67% of respondents** said they were either “very” or “extremely” concerned about the issue. The level of concern is **similar across major demographic groups**. **Air pollution was the sixth most likely local issue to be raised by respondents**, suggesting that air pollution is a critical problem in people’s lives.

Mitigation is seen as the shared responsibility for governments, businesses and citizens alike: The surveyed individuals believe that **the responsibility for reducing air pollution** is shared among various actors. When asked who should take the lead, 25% selected local government, 23% national government, and 21% citizens themselves. Businesses were also seen as responsible by 17% of respondents. There is a clear consensus that action from multiple sectors is required to effectively tackle the city’s air pollution challenges. Furthermore, approximately 80% of respondents believe that all these groups (governments, businesses, and citizens) are **currently doing too little** to address the problem. This highlights a strong public demand for **increased effort and accountability from all stakeholders**.

Strong demand for most air pollution policies: Respondents expressed strong support for a range of policies aimed at reducing air pollution: **Fines for waste burning** (82%) and **increased information** about air pollution’s health impacts (78%) were especially popular. Support for regulating industry, even if it leads to higher prices for certain products, was also high (70%). However, **support was more moderate** for policies such as expanding household electrification (56%) and expanding public transportation at higher prices (45%). **Support for banning older vehicles was lowest**, with only 37% of respondents in favour, suggesting that policies perceived as costly or personally restrictive may face resistance.

Key take-aways: Air pollution is a deeply felt concern for many people in Johannesburg, and there is broad agreement that responsibility for addressing the issue should be shared among governments, businesses, and citizens. We find strong support for most policies, but they are more cautious about policies that impose costs or limit personal choices.

Based upon these findings, we identify several recommendations for policymakers and air pollution stakeholders in Johannesburg

1. Adopting policies with broad support, such as increased fines for waste burning, information campaigns, and stricter regulations for industries.
2. Increasing support for less popular but effective policies – such as expanded public transportation, and vehicle restrictions – by making them more “fair”, such as including financial aid for vehicle replacement, or targeted exemptions for vulnerable populations.
3. Communicating the benefits effectively and engaging with communities to build trust can promote a sense of shared responsibility across society.

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Johannesburg: City Overview

PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} levels have increased in Johannesburg between 2021 and 2023¹, with peak concentrations typically occurring during the winter months in the Southern Hemisphere. Throughout this period, both pollutants consistently exceeded the World Health Organization's recommended safety guidelines. Average concentrations reached 47.5 µg/m³ for PM₁₀ and 25.6 µg/m³ for PM_{2.5}, which are approximately three times and five times higher, respectively, than the WHO's annual limits.

Monthly PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} Levels, 2021-2023, Johannesburg

Johannesburg

\$13,400 GDP per Capita

2,924/km² Population Density

South Africa

0.65 Liberal Democracy V-Dem Index

0.67 Gini Coefficient

Johannesburg is the most populated city in South Africa, the world's most economically unequal country (Gini: 0.67)².

Politically, South Africa is classified as a liberal democracy, with a 0.65 score on the Liberal Democracy Index³. Johannesburg has a moderate population density⁴ of 2,924 people/km² and an estimated GDP per capita of \$13,400⁵.

In South Africa, Air Pollution Is Responsible for⁶:

About 32,000 South Africans are estimated to die prematurely due to air pollution every year⁷. Children are especially at risk, with about 3,365 children under five years old dying prematurely in 2021⁸.

2025 Survey in Johannesburg

The data presented in this report are from surveys of people living in Johannesburg, between January and February 2025. Respondents for this survey were recruited in two distinct ways. First, an online-based sample (n=1,755) was recruited via a commercial online panel provider (Dynata). Quota-based sampling methods were used to ensure representativeness of the city population with respect to age (18-59 years) and gender.

Second, an in-person survey (n=1,251) was conducted via Computer Assisted Personal Interview (CAPI) methods that oversampled respondents from lower-income neighbourhoods following a GIS-based sampling strategy. This was done to reach individuals that would not be able to take part in the online survey, due to illiteracy or lacking internet access. Survey quality was ensured through two attention checks and a minimum completion time based on the soft launch median; respondents who failed two or more of these checks were excluded from the final sample.

In total, the study surveyed 3,006 participants from both online and in-person samples. The combined sample consisted of 57% women and 43% men. The largest age group represented was 18-29 years (33%), followed by the 30-39 and 40-49 age groups.

The most common educational attainment among participants was a matriculation certificate (matric). Respondents were residents from across the municipality, with the highest concentration coming from the Johannesburg inner city (see map above).

Education Level Distribution

Age Level Distribution

Salience of and Concern About Air Pollution

Salience of Air Pollution

For the first survey item, we presented respondents with a list of 10 problems that people in Johannesburg could be facing. We then asked them to select 3 of the most important ones. Air pollution was selected as the sixth most frequently cited issue. Overall, the three most prominent problems were public safety, government corruption, and respondents' personal economic situation.

Ranking of Most Important Problems in Johannesburg:

1. Public Safety
2. Government Corruption
3. Personal Economic Situation
4. Reliable and Affordable Access to Electricity
5. Problems With Road Infrastructure
- 6. Air Pollution**
7. Quality of Healthcare
8. Access to Clean Water
9. Affordability of Housing
10. Inequality and Discrimination

Concern About Air Pollution

Overall, we find that a majority among respondents (67%) are either “very” (44%) or “extremely” (23%) concerned. Meanwhile, 27% are “somewhat concerned”, and a small minority (6%) stated they were “not at all concerned.”

The distribution of concern is largely consistent across gender, education, and age groups, with some minor differences. Women are slightly more concerned than men.

In addition, young people are less likely to say that they are “extremely” or “very concerned” (61% of individuals in the 18-29 age group). In contrast, respondents aged 50-59 are more likely to be either “very” or “extremely concerned” (72%).

Finally, respondents with low and medium levels of education are more likely to be “not at all concerned” (9% and 7% respectively). At the same time, less-educated respondents, who are likely to be most exposed to air pollution, are also more often “extremely concerned” (45%). This attests to greater polarisation in levels of concern within this group.

Overall, the data suggest that concern about air pollution is deep and widespread, with minor socio-demographic differences in degree.

Levels of Concern About Air Pollution by Socio-Demographics

Sources of Air Pollution

We presented respondents in Johannesburg with a list of 8 potential sources of air pollution, and we asked them to select the three sources they think cause most pollution. Waste burning (1) and transportation (2) were perceived to contribute most to local air pollution. This is followed by industry (3), wildfire smoke, sand and dust (4), as well as power plants (5).

In comparison to a scientific assessment of air pollution sources in Johannesburg⁷, some of the sources overlap: such as power plants (1), industry (3) and waste burning (4). However, other large sources of air pollution were less likely to be noted by respondents, such as heating and cooking (2) as well as construction (4).

These findings suggest there is still a gap between the public perception and scientific assessments of air pollution sources. While respondents do identify many major contributors, other prominent sources like household heating and cooking or construction remain largely invisible to the public. This gap highlights the potential for targeted communication campaign to improve localised knowledge about the sources of air pollution - a crucial element in fostering individual behaviour change and support for policies that address these sources.

Perceptions of Sources vs. Prioritisation of Action for Air Pollution

The study then examined how respondents' perception of air pollution sources aligned with how much priority they wanted their government to give to actions that reduce pollution from these sources. On the left, we show the sources that respondents perceive to contribute most to air pollution, and on the right, we show the most prioritised sources for government action. This allows us to compare the relative ranking of perceived and prioritised sources.

Perceptions of Sources vs. Prioritisation of Action for Air Pollution

Overall, there is a general alignment between the two. For example, most perceive waste burning to be a major source of pollution (24%) and want the government to prioritise it for policy action (22%). However, a few notable discrepancies emerge, too.

In some cases, respondents were more likely to think a source contributed to air pollution but less likely to prioritise it for government action. For instance, transportation was named as a major source by 19% of those surveyed, but 16% listed it as a priority for the government.

In other cases, respondents were more likely to support government action on a source than to name it as a major cause of pollution. For example, while 9% viewed power plants as a top source, 13% felt the government should give them priority for policy measures.

Overall, the results show both general alignment and slight differences between the perceptions of air pollution sources and priorities for government action. In addition, the findings suggest a clear mandate from citizens for the government to place emphasis on waste burning, industry, and transportation.

Air Pollution Reduction Responsibilities

Who Is Responsible for Air Pollution Reduction?

In addition, businesses (17%) were selected quite frequently, suggesting that they also bear great responsibility for the reduction of air pollution.

Meanwhile, experts (11%) and international organisations (3%) were chosen less often as the main responsible actors.

How Much Are Actors Doing to Reduce Air Pollution?

Notably, citizens are held to similar standards as institutional actors by respondents, reinforcing the idea that tackling air pollution requires both government leadership and community engagement.

Air Pollution Reduction

We also asked respondents who they thought was most responsible for reducing air pollution. They could select up to three institutional or societal actors.

Local government (25%), national government (23%) and citizens (21%) were most often chosen as responsible for fighting air pollution. These findings suggest that while responsibility is seen as shared across society, there is a strong expectation that government, particularly at the local and national level, should take the lead in addressing air pollution. This perception is consistent with the notion of air pollution as a systemic issue, necessitating direct policy action and regulation, as opposed to reliance on individual and voluntary change.

Action on Air Pollution Reduction

Moreover, we asked respondents about how much local government, businesses and citizens are doing to reduce air pollution. Overall, about 80% of people think that all three groups are either not doing enough or too little to reduce air pollution.

These findings suggest that the public sees air pollution reduction as a shared responsibility between government, businesses and citizens, with widespread demand for all three to become more involved.

Public Demand for Air Pollution Policies

Public Demand for Air Pollution Policies

To better understand public preferences for various governmental measures to reduce air pollution, we asked respondents to evaluate six distinct policies. The potential governmental measures range from bans and limitations, such as prohibiting older vehicles or fines for waste burning, to low-cost measures, such as more information about the health impacts of air pollution. In addition, some policies combine regulatory effort with moderate costs, including increased household electrification, expanding public transportation, and regulating polluting industries.

Overall, we find substantial support for many of these policies. Over 50% of respondents are either in favour or strongly in favour of increased fines on waste burning (82%), more information on air pollution's health effects (78%), regulating industries (70%) and expanding household electrification (56%). In particular, fines for waste burning and more information appear to have very deep support, with just 11% against or strongly against them.

Preferences towards expanding public transportation were more mixed, with 45% of respondents in favour, but 37% against. We also find comparatively more resistance to banning older vehicles, as 37% support and 44% oppose the policy. This suggests potential public pushback against policies that directly restrict individual behaviour (e.g. choice of car).

Support for Regulating Industry by Socio-Demographics

Regulations on Industry

However, how do individual policy preferences vary by socio-demographic characteristics? In terms of regulating industries (even at the potential cost of increased prices for their products), overall support (70%) is similar across different genders and age groups. Respondents aged 30-39 are slightly more in favour (73%), while 50-59-year-olds show lower levels of support (67%).

Support varies more substantially by respondents' level of education. While highly educated respondents are somewhat more in favour (76%), substantially less people with low education levels agree (58%). The latter are also more often against the policy (32%).

We see this particular pattern of polarisation across policies in Johannesburg, which could be because less educated people were more often surveyed in person. In person responses were more likely to be at the pole of the question scale (strongly in favour/strongly against), likely due to the questions being read out loud during many in-person interviews.

Nonetheless, most respondents favour more stringent industry regulation across all socio-demographic indicators, suggesting widespread demand for it. Public communication and policy design could be adapted to address different concerns for different age groups and levels of education, while still taking advantage of strong overall support for action.

Electricity Access

Next, we explore the varying levels of public support for expanding household electrification, even at the potential cost of higher electricity prices. The policy is favoured by a slight majority (56%), with particular variation in the degree of support for different levels of education.

Men are slightly more supportive (59%) than women (53%). Older respondents (50-59) are both less in favour (50%) and more against (32%) the policy, compared to all other age groups. Highly educated respondents are substantially less likely to strongly prefer the policy (26%), compared to those with lower educational attainment (54%).

Though endorsed by majorities across socio-demographic groups, support runs less deep. This suggests that policies with direct cost implications, even if tied to long-term benefits like cleaner energy, may be met with softer support, especially among highly educated respondents.

Support for Expanding Electricity Access by Socio-Demographics

Public Transportation

We then focus on socio-demographic variation in support for expanding public transportation, which would be financed by increasing ticket prices. Here, our data shows considerably lower overall support (45%), with minor divergence in preferences across age and gender, and more pronounced differences by educational attainment.

Support among respondents aged 50-59 is slightly lower at 40%, compared to other age groups. Stronger endorsement of the policy again appears less frequently among respondents with advanced education, while those with less education show higher degrees of support and opposition.

The expansion of public transportation falls short of overall support over 50%, with no majorities found among any socio-demographic group.

Support for Expanding Public Transportation by Socio-Demographics

Ban on Old Vehicles

Finally, we examine respondents' response to banning older vehicles, with results broken down by socio-demographic characteristics. Overall, the policy receives limited public support, as 37% of respondents are in favour, compared to 44% opposed, with minor divergences across gender and age.

Instead, attitudes toward the policy vary particularly by level of education. Respondents with higher education are less likely to be supportive of the policy (35%). In contrast, those with lower levels of education are considerably more likely to express both support (49%) for and opposition (50%) to it.

In sum, while a ban on older vehicles garners limited support, it falls short of majority endorsements in any socio-demographic group.

Support for Banning Old Vehicles by Socio-Demographics

Air Pollution Policy Support Across Middle-Income Cities

We also compare support levels for air pollution policies in Johannesburg to those in three major middle-income cities: Accra (Ghana), Jakarta (Indonesia), and Delhi (India).

Comparison of Air Pollution Policy Support in Middle-Income Cities

While attitudes towards air pollution policies are generally positive in Johannesburg, public support tends to be lower than in Delhi, Jakarta, and Accra. For example, as stricter industry regulation is favoured by 70% of respondents in Johannesburg, public support for the policy is substantially higher in Jakarta (80%), Accra (81%), and Delhi (84%).

The most notable differences appear in transportation-related and electrification policies. A sizable number of respondents (44%) in Johannesburg oppose banning old vehicles, and 37% are against public transportation expansion. Opposition to increased electrification is also comparatively strong at 29%, higher than in the other three cities.

These results suggest that respondents in Johannesburg are more cautious toward policies with visible or immediate personal costs, compared to their counterparts in other middle-income cities.

Overall, public support for air pollution policies remains strong, even when costs are made explicit. However, the variation across cities shows that policy preferences are shaped by local context, highlighting the importance of tailoring solutions to specific urban settings and public priorities.

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